

Veterinary Legislation And The Organisation Of Veterinary Supervision In The Polish Lands, 1774–1918

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ABSTRACT

The first Polish legal regulations concerning veterinary medicine date from the second half of the eighteenth century. In 1774, a parliamentary constitution was adopted that obliged physicians to supervise hospital districts in order to prevent the spread of cattle and sheep plague. In 1780, the Royal Commission of Good Order issued 46 regulations governing animal slaughter and the meat trade. During the Duchy of Warsaw, the first normative act devoted exclusively to animal health protection was introduced: the 'Regulations for the Rescue of Horned Cattle in Present Diseases, together with Measures Sufficient to Safeguard them from the Immediate Spread of Mortality'. In 1844, the 'Veterinary Police Act' was issued in Warsaw, becoming the first piece of legislation to define in detail the tasks of state administrative bodies responsible for veterinary matters. During the period of partition, the laws of the partitioning powers remained in force. At the turn of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, veterinary services in the Polish lands developed differently in each partition, as did the relevant legal regulations. The restoration of independence in 1918 led to the unification of veterinary administration and the introduction of new legal solutions.

Keywords: veterinary law; history of veterinary medicine; infectious animal diseases

INTRODUCTION

The organisation of veterinary supervision over animal husbandry and, in particular, the prevention of the spread of infectious diseases and the protection of public health in relation to food of animal origin has a long history. It predates the establishment of organised veterinary education, that is, the founding of the veterinary school in Lyon in 1762. From the outset, these activities were based on the concept of administrative veterinary police, and this remains the case today. The tasks of such an organisation were, and still are, to protect public welfare and safety in the broadest sense [1]. An administrative apparatus organised in this way employs instruments affecting the

economic sphere, especially rationing and regulation, as well as mechanisms of supervision, control and enforcement of the law in force [2].

EARLY LEGISLATION IN THE POLISH–LITHUANIAN COMMONWEALTH

In Poland, the first police authority appeared during the Four-Year Sejm as one of the five departments of the Permanent Council. Its competences included, among other things, supervision of hygienic and sanitary conditions in the country [3].

The first legal regulations concerning veterinary matters date from the second half of the eighteenth century. In 1774, a parliamentary constitution was enacted as part of this administrative framework. It obliged physicians and feldshers to supervise hospital districts in order to prevent the spread of cattle and sheep plague [4]. In 1780, the Royal Commission of Good Order issued 46 regulations governing the slaughter of animals and the meat trade. This set of provisions significantly limited the guild monopoly and regulated both slaughter practices and sanitary supervision over the quality of animal products placed on the market [5].

Despite the introduction of these regulations, compliance appears to have been inadequate. A municipal and national physician in the Austrian partition wrote in a report of 1772 about the condition of sanitary law: ‘Among the various disorders of the Polish government, not the least concerns medicine. The Poles, slaves to mindless freedom, refused even, for the sake of their own health and lives, to restrain it’ [5]. Similarly, in about 1791, the intendant of the Sandomierz department reported to the Police Commission on sanitary conditions: ‘The habitual uncleanness in Polish towns would have to come to an end (...) the excrement which they do not usually bury, but throw into the streets and onto the roads, infects the air to the point of causing disease. Those who cast out foul matter and fail to bury carcasses are unlikely to obey until they are fined’ [6].

These opinions referred not only to the hygienic condition of the population but also to the danger of spreading animal diseases. It was only in the period of the Duchy of Warsaw that the first normative act devoted exclusively to animal health protection was introduced. This document, entitled the ‘Rules for the Rescue of Horned Cattle in Present Diseases, together with Sufficient Measures to Protect Them from the Imminent Spread of Mortality’, listed primarily those diseases that, before 1807, had caused major losses among domestic animals, including cattle [6]. The regulations required notification of every case of disease listed in the document and provided for the issuing of police and veterinary orders in the event of an epidemic. One important measure intended to limit the spread of disease was the possibility of establishing ‘isolation stables for sick cattle’ [6].

Another step towards stricter supervision over the movement of animals was the introduction of certificates confirming that animals came from areas free of contagious disease. This was regulated by a Police Order on the bringing of cattle to fairs and markets,

issued on 3 October 1810 by the Minister of Police, Aleksander Potocki. Village heads, mayors and landowners were responsible for issuing such certificates. The absence of this document resulted in the removal of animals from the market [6].

REGULATIONS IN THE KINGDOM OF POLAND

In 1844, the ‘Veterinary Police Act, or regulations to prevent and suppress prevailing and contagious diseases among domestic animals’ was issued in Warsaw (Fig. 1). This was the first piece of legislation to define in some detail the tasks of state administrative bodies responsible for veterinary matters [7].

Figure 1. Title page of the Act

The regulations defined the competences and duties of government physicians and standardised the rules of cooperation between local police officials and government physicians, entrusting the former with extensive duties relating to information and reporting on the condition of animal health observed in the field. Certain responsibilities were imposed on the Government Commission for Internal Affairs, as well as on civil governors, district chiefs, parish priests and local administrators. The duties of the government physician included, first and foremost, attending the place where disease had appeared on the basis of information provided by a police official. In cases that did not require personal intervention, the physician could issue appropriate medical recommendations remotely. The occurrence of cattle plague obliged the Government Commission for Internal Affairs to notify all civil governors, who in turn had to inform the district chiefs. Parish priests or administrators were required to inform the population during church services about the signs of infectious disease, as specified in writing by the government physician [7].

The Act divided diseases into two classes: 'prevailing contagious diseases' and 'prevailing non-contagious diseases'. It described clinical signs, disease course and post-mortem lesions. It was also one of the first regulations to include elements of differential diagnosis and to discuss disease causation.

In the case of tuberculosis, the 1844 Act classified it in the second group, that is, among prevailing non-contagious diseases. Severe tuberculous lesions rendered the meat unfit for consumption. The restrictions applied not only to meat but also to milk. The consumption of milk from animals showing symptoms of, among other conditions, tuberculosis was prohibited. In practice, the legislator was therefore, probably unknowingly, limiting the spread of acid-fast mycobacteria.

VETERINARY LEGISLATION IN THE AUSTRIAN PARTITION

Following the introduction of the constitutional system in the Habsburg monarchy, the statutory tasks of the administration included supervision of the implementation and observance of health legislation. According to Section 2(c) of the Act on the organisation of the public health service of 30 April 1870, officials were to ensure compliance with 'laws on contagious diseases, endemics, epidemics and contagious cattle diseases, as well as quarantine and contumacy stations for cattle and the trade in poisons and medicines' [8]. In the Austrian partition, veterinary supervision and control were regulated in order to improve sanitary conditions in human settlements and strengthen veterinary oversight of livestock on farms. The principal aim was to reduce epidemiological risk. Surveillance was exercised by government physicians and district veterinarians, who were obliged to report outbreaks of mass disease among farm animals [9].

Among the infectious diseases that attracted particular attention from the state apparatus was tuberculosis, which was regarded as a potential zoonotic disease. The eradication of animal diseases in the Habsburg monarchy was difficult owing to both cost and, above all, the vast extent of the territory. Nevertheless, Austrian legislators subjected animal husbandry to detailed epidemiological regulation. The Act of 29 June 1868 on infectious diseases of cattle should be noted first [10]. It made animal passports issued by municipal authorities compulsory in areas declared to be at epidemic risk [11]. In turn, the Act of 2 May 1873 regulated the marketing of meat and hides from healthy animals slaughtered in areas threatened by plague; this also applied to cattle [12]. Another important legal act was the Act on the Suppression of Contagious Animal Diseases of 29 February 1880 [13].

Its provisions set out rules for dealing with animals when an infectious disease was detected on farms. The Act maintained a system of animal vaccination carried out under the supervision of 'official veterinarians'. It also introduced the concept of quarantine, imposed, inter alia, on barns in which animals were kept. Implementing regulations issued jointly by the Ministries of the Interior, Justice, Agriculture and Commerce on 19 March 1883 specified detailed procedures for handling animals, including the prohibition on using animals suspected of disease for field work, the isolation of healthy animals from diseased or suspected animals, and restrictions on animals that had recovered from disease, including a one-year ban on their release [14].

The problem of animal diseases and zoonoses in the Habsburg monarchy was comprehensively regulated by the Act of 6 August 1909 on the prevention and suppression of contagious animal diseases [15]. This Act introduced detailed procedures to be followed by district and national authorities during epidemics. Veterinary institutions, ranging from the Veterinary Academy in Lviv to state laboratories and vaccine production facilities outside the Academy structure, played an important role. Municipalities were obliged to issue passports for livestock, and cattle were treated with particular care, each animal having to possess an individual passport. The absence of such a document automatically excluded an animal from the market. Veterinarians were required to inspect not only the animals themselves but also the facilities in which they were housed, as well as railway stations designated by district authorities for animal transport. In justified cases, when the affected area expanded, district authorities could, at the request of a veterinarian, introduce special precautionary measures, including declaring a given locality closed [15]. The provisions of these Acts concerned infectious animal diseases in general and also applied to bovine tuberculosis.

VETERINARY LEGISLATION IN THE PRUSSIAN PARTITION

The legislation in force in the former Prussian partition was more concerned with food products of animal origin than with the control of infectious diseases. The principal Act requiring the disposal of animals showing symptoms of tuberculosis was the Act on the Inspection of Slaughter Animals and Meat of 3 June 1900 [16]. This was not the only legal instrument regulating the conduct of veterinary and sanitary inspection authorities. In the context of tuberculosis control, mention should also be made of the Animal Diseases Act of 26 July 1909 [16] and the Implementing Act on Contagious Diseases of Domestic Animals of 25 July 1911 [17].

Implementation of these provisions was distributed among various administrative units. The partition was divided into counties grouped into regencies. In each district, the district veterinarian was subordinate to the veterinary decision-making authority within the presidential department of the regency, namely the veterinary regency councillor. The tasks of the state veterinary service included chiefly the control of infectious diseases, among them bovine tuberculosis, and the supervision of food of animal origin. Particular attention was paid to the open form of tuberculosis, and animals showing such symptoms were eliminated from further use. Statutory isolation facilities were also introduced for cows reacting positively to the tuberculin test, and restrictions were imposed on the movement of animals suspected of having the disease. As in the other partitions, cattle were provided with certificates of place of origin, commonly referred to as passports [16].

CONCLUSION

The veterinary service in the Polish lands at the turn of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries developed differently in each of the three partitions, and this also applied to legal regulations. Only after the restoration of independence in 1918 was the functioning of veterinary administration standardised and new legal solutions introduced. After independence had been regained, the idea of creating a veterinary administration was based on the principles of administrative police.

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